

EXPLORATORY ACTION RESEARCH IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. *In this article, the study of discovery movements in English lessons. Knowledge of a foreign language is an important factor in mastering the secrets of any profession, gaining qualifications and skills. Knowledge of a foreign language represents a higher level of qualification of a specialist who is active in any field of the national economy. A foreign language can now also be seen in various fields, and its role in the educational process is incomparable. This article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of creating virtual resources based on imitation models in English lessons.*

Keywords: *Foreign Language, English, imitation models, virtual resources, skills.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ДЕЙСТВИЙ В КЛАССАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье: исследование движения Дискавери в английских лекциях. Knowledge of a foreign language is an important factor in mastering the secrets of any Professional, gaining qualifications and skills. Знание иностранного языка репрезентирует высокий уровень квалификации специалиста кто активен в любом поле национальной экономики. A foreign language can now also be seen in various fields, and its role in the educational process is incomparable. Эти обложки произведений the theoretical and practical aspects of creating Virtual Resources based on imitation models in English lessons.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннный язык, английский, имитационные модели, виртуальные ресурсы, навыки.*

Most of the electronic textbooks created for foreign language educational institutions covered objects in the curriculum of general educational schools and Lyceum colleges. It is known that the study of a foreign language is currently carried out from the 1st grade. In this regard, the emphasis on a foreign language increased. In order to activate educational processes, various books were created interesting interactive lesson maps. However, along with such work, the need for vertical resources in classes began to be felt. The problems of increased attention to a foreign language by the Ministry of public education through the implementation of various, the interesting transition of lesson processes through computer imitation models were thrown into the middle. The line is now becoming very popular.

Knowledge of a foreign language is an important factor in mastering the secrets of any profession, gaining qualifications and skills. Knowledge of a foreign language represents a higher level of qualification of a specialist who is active in any field of the national economy. For this reason, even if graduates of Secondary Schools have not set the goal of entering a higher educational institution, their deep study of a foreign language and acquisition of free-speech skills are very necessary for future specialists who aim to operate in various fields of national economy. Among the most effective approaches to teaching a foreign language, through the means of Information Communication Technologies, it is possible to show language teaching methodologies in distance learning. Computer technology has a very wide range of possibilities, especially in language learning using the Internet. They are manifested in the following:

1) to actively use in practice the acquired knowledge and skills in oral relations in a foreign language and learn to use the language materials received not only in his speech, but also in understanding the speech of an interlocutor whom he met through the Internet;

2) formation of a flexible skill to transfer acquired speech knowledge to changing situations of the relationship;

3) to organize a conversation that is carried out in the form of informal communication, to create a strong, immediate motivation to learn to speak and a motivation to react close to reality;

4) overcoming psychological barriers, in particular, avoiding speaking a foreign language and making mistakes, removing the barrier and internal and external reluctance, as well as the feeling of shame;

5) a high level of educational quality and immediate effectiveness; as soon as the training is the second exercise, users begin to speak a foreign language that they are learning in a colloquial mold given in the main training text; the use of text impact suggestive tools (including memory input) is used, and classes are taken into account as early as the first exercise;

The increase in educational performance from quantitative to qualitative consists in revising the proportions between home and classroom work of teaching to all types of speech activity using suggestopedic technology in favor of classroom work, and building new features of the interaction of the user and users with each other.

Time distribution is the main important difference of the accelerated method from the traditional one

The intensive method for studying a school program in a foreign language cannot be applied in full size.

Individual methods of intensive method can be successfully used in foreign language lessons at school. It is known that the 60-70 years of the last century are considered as a period of the emergence and development of new methods of teaching a number of foreign languages, known under the general name "intensive teaching method". All these methods, which originally arose in different countries and in different years of this period, are nevertheless a general response of the methodology to the social order of modern society.

The growing number of specialists in various fields of Science and technology, which directly carry out international scientific and technical relations, which occurs with the international situation of this period, the scientific and technical revolution that caused the "explosion" of information, and the expansion of the circle of cultural and practical contacts, all this put their requirements on the need to know a foreign language.

The conditions of relations in a foreign language, in which a foreign language is considered a means of communication, knowledge, obtaining and collecting information, determine the need to know all types of speech activity: understanding and reading this foreign language, writing, the degree of knowledge of one or another type of speech activity, directly in the practice of communication in a foreign language, reading it is manifested in the exchange of written information in its form.

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